

Research

Election Management Autonomy: A Case of Election Commission of Pakistan

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Abstract: Free, fair and transparent elections provide fundamental legitimacy to democratic process. An independent Election Management Body (EMB) is considered prerequisite for conducting free, fair and transparent elections. Most of the empirical research on the relationship between the independence of Election Management body and free, fair and transparent elections demonstrates a muted relationship (Birch, 2008; Birch, 2010; Rosas, 2010). The conventional models used by Birch (2008), Birch (2010) and Rosas (2010) are not sufficient to evaluate the independence of EMB and this research used van Aaken (2009) conceptual framework to assess and evaluate the independence of Election Commission of Pakistan by using a qualitative research method based on primary data through interviews and primary documents. The findings indicate that the institutional, functional, financial and personal autonomy are closely connected with each other. Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) enjoys sufficient autonomy institutionally but judicial activism, judicial outreach and lack of financial autonomy restricts it from exercise its overall autonomy independently.

Keywords: Elections, Election Management Body, Autonomy, Election Commission of Pakistan.

1 Introduction

Multi-party elections have become the norm of a democratic polity (Moehler, 2009) and trust of citizens in transparency of elections has become vital to provide legitimacy to the democratic process (Rose & Mishler, 2009). Free, fair and transparent elections are the cornerstone of a democratic process and provide legitimacy to an incumbent democratic government (Mozaffar & Schedler, 2002; Lehoucq, 2002). Elections are known as an evolutionary process, bring about peaceful changes in the political process (Goodwin-gill, 2006).

In diverse societies like Pakistan which are facing ethnocentric conflicts, free and fair elections become even more crucial, as they can lead to manage the conflicts and to squeeze down the differences in a federal system of government (PILDAT, 2012). Goodwin-gill (2006) states that, “in any State the authority of the government can only be derived from the will of the people as expressed in genuine, free and fair elections held at regular intervals on the basis of universal, equal and secret suffrage”.

Scholars have widely recognized the autonomy of Election Management Bodies (EMBs) pre-requisite for electoral credibility (Pastor, 1999; Mozaffar, 2002). Autonomous Election Management Bodies (EMBs) ensure both horizontal and vertical accountability during election by ensuring the citizens right to vote during elections and by holding political elites accountable to the rules and regulations of elections.

Pakistan has a poor electoral history and experience. Pakistan has witnessed eleven general elections since its independence. However, most national and international observers hold strong reservations about the neutrality and transparency of those elections. Free, fair and transparent elections depend on an enabling legislative framework, impartial election commission, and free media, forces that maintain law and order and acceptance of the competitive electoral process by all the political forces in the country.

For conducting elections in the country, a constitutional institution exists in Pakistan. Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) was established for the first time under 1956 constitution. The constitution of Pakistan, 1973 also provides for establishment of an independent election commission, charged with the duties of preparing electoral rolls, their annual revision and organizing and conducting elections to the assemblies.

There has been a lack of confidence among election stakeholders in the independence and performance of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) (FAFEN, 2017). The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has been lacking transparency in the key areas of its working practices, and did not formally consult with political parties and other stakeholders. Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has been strongly criticized for its poor performance in elections management. This research develops a relationship between ‘autonomy of Election Management Body (EBM)’ and ‘clean elections’. It applies the framework developed by (van Aaken, 2009a) to measure autonomy of Election Management Bodies (EMBs) under dimensions including institutional, personal, financial and functional autonomy.

The research is an attempt to answers the following core questions.

1. What is the level of autonomy of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) to hold free and fair elections in Pakistan?
2. What are factors which contribute to restrain the institutional, functional, financial and personal autonomies of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP)?

2 Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP): A Brief Overview

The constitution of Pakistan provides for establishment of an independent Election Commission to conduct elections at national, provincial as well as local level.

2.1 Status and Mandate of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP)

Article 218 of the Constitution of Pakistan, 1973 provides for establishment of a permanent, autonomous, and independent election commission to conduct elections for Parliament (National Assembly and the Senate), the four provincial assemblies, and local governments. It further asks to conduct elections to “other public offices as may be specified by law”, for instance, office of President (The Constitution of Pakistan, 1973). Article 220 of the constitution of Pakistan, 1973 bounds all executive authorities at federal as well as provincial level to support Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) in executing its functions and duties (The Constitution of Pakistan, 1973) Furthermore, the Representation of the People Act (1976) authorizes the commission to request any support, including “any such vehicle, vessel or animal”, for the purpose of transportation of election material including staff and ballot boxes. Article 219 of Constitution of Pakistan, 1973 provides the commission with the mandate to prepare electoral rolls for all kind of elections and their annual revision; conducting by-elections to fill casual vacancies; and to settle electoral complaints by appointing tribunals (The Constitution of Pakistan, 1973).

2.2 Composition of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP)

Article 213 of Constitution of Pakistan, 1973 provides for appointment of a Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) who would be the head of commission and four members, one from each province (The Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, 1973). Originally, the constitution had made it mandatory for Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) and other members must be retired judges of higher judiciary (Supreme Court or High Court). However, in 2016, the Parliament through 22nd constitutional amendment in the Constitution of Pakistan, 1973 allowed

for the technocrats and top bureaucrats to be appointed as members as well as Chief Election Commissioner (The Constitution of Pakistan, 1973).

The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has its headquarters in Islamabad Capital territory (ICT), and has offices in each provincial capital as well as at divisional and district level units across the country. The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has more than 1,800 officials; most of them are long-term employees (ECP, 2013). The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has four joint secretaries that manage four wings (Strategic plan, 2010-14):

1. Election Operations
2. Training, research and evaluation human resource
3. Administration
4. Budget and finance.

The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) also has two directorates; an Information Technology (IT) directorate headed by a Director General (DG) and a Public Relations (PR) directorate which is headed by a director.

3 Models of Election Management Bodies

A holistic design shapes a country's electoral management process. Also, the state's indigenous administrative setup remains at the core of electoral management. Colonial patterns of administration may be observed prominently in electoral management in post-colonial era. Despite a lot number of variations of details, three broad types or models of Electoral Management Bodies (EMB) have been identified by Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance (IDEA) – the Independent Model (IM), Governmental Model (GM) and Mixed Models (MM) (IDEA, 2006.)

3.1 The Independent Model (IM)

The Independent Model (IM) of electoral management exists in those countries where elections are organized and managed by an Election Management Body (EMB) which is institutionally independent and autonomous from the executive branch of government, and which has its own budget and also manages it (IDEA, 2006). Under the Independent Model (IM), an Election Management Body (EMB) is not accountable to a government ministry or department. It may be accountable to the legislature, the judiciary, or the head of state. Election Management Bodies (EMBs) under the Independent Model (IM) may enjoy varying degrees of financial autonomy and accountability, as well as varying levels of performance accountability. They are

composed of members who are outside the executive while in an election management body (Ellis et al., 2014).

3.2 The Governmental Model (GM)

The Governmental Model (GM) of electoral management exists in those countries where elections are organized and managed by the executive branch. They are led by a minister or civil servant and is answerable to a Cabinet minister (Ellis et al., 2014)

3.3 The Mixed Model (MM)

In the Mixed Model (MM) of electoral management, the Election Management Bodies (EMB) consist of two wings: a policy, monitoring or supervisory wing that is independent of the executive branch of government and an implementation wing located within a department of state or local government (IDEA, 2006)

4 Election Management Autonomy

Election Management Bodies (EMBs), depending on their characteristics, prevent intentional rigging and or administrative inadequacies. As pointed out by Aaken (2009b), “Whereas independent central banks or audit courts control special issue areas of politics, Election Management Bodies (EMBs) control the moment of the set-up of government—the election; a crucial moment as the de-facto accountability of governments depends on it (van Aaken, 2009b)”. He further argues that the institutional framework of Election Management Bodies (EMBs) and their independence from executive branch of government is one of the most important variables affecting the quality of fairness of election in a country. He refers the independent Election Management Bodies (EMBs), as the outsourced agencies for free and fair elections. In modern democracies, elections are considered as matter of routine. An independent Election Management Body (EMB) is less needed in such states where bureaucracy is perceived as neutral, efficient and trusted. Aaken (2009b) argues that a completely flawless election is impossible to occur (Aaken, 2009b). Counting errors, incomplete registration of voters and small inadequacies may occur quite often. However, till the time these errors occur randomly, they can be accommodated and credibility of elections is not at stake. These are minor administrative issues and are not intentional. The scale of potential administrative fraud is quite small in an independent system.

To measure the autonomy of an EMB, Aaken (2009b) has hypothesized a conceptual framework which separates autonomy in four heads (van Aaken, 2009b):

- I. Institutional Autonomy (IA)
- II. Financial Autonomy (FA)
- III. Personal Autonomy (PA)
- IV. Functional Autonomy (FA)

4.1 Institutional Autonomy

Independence is an essential characteristic of an institution responsible for conducting elections. While the structure of Election Management Bodies (EMBs) vary from country to country, those Election Management Bodies (EMBs) are considered as the most successful that offer both a perceived and real tradition of impartiality at all levels of organization. “To establish the integrity and credibility of electoral processes and promote the widespread acceptance of election results, it is critical that an [election commission] not only conducts electoral events in a fearlessly independent manner, but that it is impartial in its actions,” (Garnett, 2019).

The United Nations Organization (UNO) has stated clearly that, in every country provisions of law should ensure that an “objective, unbiased, independent and effective administrative structure [for conducting elections] is in place.” In achieving this end, careful attention must be given to those provisions focusing on appointment, remuneration, duties and powers, qualifications, and reporting structures in the context of election administration (Wally et al., 2014).

In its 2006 survey, IDEA studied 214 electoral management agencies round the globe and showed that 55% followed independent model, 26% have employed governmental model and 15% have setup Mixed Model (MM) Election Management Body (EMB) (Reynolds et al., 2005).

4.2 Financial Autonomy

4.2.1 State or Public Funding

Electoral events are a core function of a democratic state. The state thus remains the primary source of funding for the core costs of most Election Management Bodies (EMBs). The electoral budget forms part of the consolidated annual national budget, yet different models of Election Management Bodies (EMBs) may receive their funding by different methods and routes from the budget.

4.2.2 Method of Disbursing State Funding

Funding for many Election Management Bodies (EMBs) under the Independent Model (IM), for example in Albania, Ghana and Kosovo, is a separate line item in the national budget, released directly to the (EMB) by the treasury. For others, the Election Management Body (EMB) budget is released through a government ministry (Ellis et al., 2014).

Budgets for Election Management Bodies (EMBs) under the Governmental Model (GM) are usually part of the budget of the government ministry responsible for implementing electoral processes, as in Cook Islands, Denmark and Singapore. Where the Mixed Model (MM) is present, the budget of the independent wing of Election Management Body (EMB) may be channeled through a line ministry, such as the Ministry of the Interior in France (Catt, Ellis, Maley & Wall, 2015).

4.2.3 Integrated or Distributed Electoral Budgets

An electoral budget may be a single integrated item in the national budget, or may consist of many components that are spread across the budgets of various government agencies. National, regional and local governments' budgets may each provide funds to Election Management Bodies (EMBs). In the unitary state of Indonesia, the national budget fully funds the Election Management Body (EMB) to conduct presidential elections and elections to national and regional legislatures, but regional and local authorities provide most of the funding for elections for provincial governors and local mayors. Such arrangements are more common in federal states (Catt, Ellis, Maley & Wall, 2015).

Funding for the Election Management Body (EMB) in Bosnia and Herzegovina is provided by all four levels of government; their respective shares vary according to the type of elections being held. In India and Mexico, the national government funds the Election Management Body (EMB) to conduct national elections, but regional governments contribute funds when their elections coincide with national ones. Some Election Management Bodies (EMBs) receive income in the form of nomination fees, lost deposits, or fine imposed following breaches of electoral campaigning or other regulations.

Election Management Bodies (EMBs) may also receive funds and donations in kind from large corporations, the business community and philanthropists. Election Management Bodies (EMBs) need to be careful that the manner of raising funds from the corporate sector does not affect perceptions of their fine probity, impartiality or credibility. Some Election Management

Bodies (EMBs), as in Australia, raise some funds through the administration of elections on behalf of bodies such as professional associations or trade unions. Others, as in Mauritius, charge a fee to recover the costs of printing copies of the electoral register that are distributed to political parties.

4.3 Personal Autonomy

Election Management Bodies (EMBs) are composed of experts from different fields and their appointment, retirement, removal and eligibility criteria are studied under personal independence. In case of Governmental Model (GM), personal autonomy is confiscated and it all relies on government discretion. However, Mixed Model (MM) and Independent Models (IM) enjoy considerable independence from executive branch.

4.4 Functional Autonomy

Functional autonomy is the most important yet most difficult kind of autonomy. Election Management Bodies (EMBs) have to operate in a governance structure and many a time they have to hire people from bureaucracy for short term assignments especially in election seasons. This dependence on executive curtails the independence of Election Management Bodies (EMBs). Institute of Democracy and Electoral Assistance (IDEA) has distinguished the functions carried out by Election Management Bodies (EMBs) into active and passive decisions. For example, Election Management Body (EMB) has to register voters and conduct election. These are its active function while the decision on who will vote and how to vote is not direct domain of Election Management Bodies (EMBs) and these are its passive functions.

5 Research Methodology

5.1 Overall Approach

Keeping in view the used nature of research topic conceptual framework, the research used purely qualitative research techniques. For data collection, the research has chiefly relied on primary data through open ended interviews with the respondents selected through purposive sampling technique. However, secondary data like documents of ECP and elections related legislations are also used to establish informed results. Following methods are employed to collect data.

- a) Document Analysis
- b) In- depth Interviews

5.1.1 Document Analysis

All the electoral laws are not encapsulated into a single piece of legislation. The whole legal framework covering elections is dispersed in a number of laws, ordinances and rules. The operative framework includes:

- The powers and functions of the CEC and its composition are covered in articles 213-226 of 1973 Constitution of Pakistan.
- The Representation of the People Act, 1976, governing the conduct of elections to the National Assembly and Provincial Assemblies so as to guard against corrupt and illegal practices and other offenses at or in connection with such elections and for the determination of doubts and disputes arising out of or in connection with such elections.
- The Representation of the People (Conduct of Election) Rules, 1977, frames the code of conduct of elections.
- The Election Commission Order, 2002, was brought to change the composition of ECP. It has increased the members from two to four by including one member from each province.
- Elections to the Senate are held according to the Senate (Election) Act, 1975; the Senate (Election) Rules, 1975; and the Senate (Members from Federal Capital) Order, 1985.
- The Electoral Rolls Act, 1974 addresses the preparation, annual revision, amendment and maintenance of the list of eligible voters.
- The Delimitation of Constituencies Act, 1974 governs delimitation of constituencies for the National Assembly and the four provincial assemblies.
- The 18th amendment of constitution of Pakistan explains the appointment of Chief Election Commission and members of commission.
- The 22nd amendment to the constitution.
- Election Act 2017.

5.1.2 In-depth interviews

The second and chief method that is used for the collection of data is open ended in-depth interviews of various participants selected through purposive sampling technique. These are face to face discussion with 50 respondents (*Table 1*). The reason behind using purposive sampling technique is to target the respondents with particular character or nature. As the nature of study is a bit technical, therefore, specialists of electoral systems are identified and contacted to get

opinion on the technical matters. Themes and sub-themes are listed below to funnel down the scope of the study.

Table 1: Summary of Respondents

Participants	Planned Interviews	Selection Criteria
Election Commission of Pakistan	Members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serving = 1 • Retired = 1
Election Commission Secretariat	Secretary ECP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serving = 1 • Retired = 1
	Head of Admin wing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serving = 1 • Retired = 1
	Head of Budget wing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serving = 1 • Retired = 1
	Head of Training, Research & Evaluation wing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serving = 1 • Retired = 1
Experts (On Election Management/Electoral Politics)	Politicians	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Senators = 5 • MNAs = 5
	Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhD Scholars = 10.
	NGOs (Working on Electoral Politics)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experts = 10
	Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journalists = 10
	Legal Eternity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lawyers = 10
Total Respondents		50

5.2 Data Analysis

To analyze the qualitative data, ‘thematic analysis’ technique is used. Braun and Clarke (2006) have defined this technique as, ‘A method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis goes through following six stages:

- i. Familiarizing oneself with the data
- ii. Generating initial codes
- iii. Searching for the themes
- iv. Reviewing the themes
- v. Defining and naming themes
- vi. Producing the report

Thematic analysis is selected as it provides much needed flexibility which is required to view issue from different angles and perspectives. It is a best suited technique to move from broad reading of the data towards the discovering of recurrent patterns and key themes within the data (*Table 2*).

Table 2: Indicators, Themes and Sub-themes for Measuring Election Management

Indicators	Themes and Sub-themes
Institutional Autonomy	Model of EMB: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent Model • Governmental Model • Mixed Model
	Legal Framework: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dependence of ECP on Executive Branch
	Accountability mechanism: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative • Executive • Judicial
	Reforms Process
Personal Autonomy	Selection criteria of Chief Election Commissioner and members
	Selection process
	Removal mechanism
	Security of tenure.
Financial Autonomy	Determination of Budget: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive • Legislature
	Expenditure Control
Functional Autonomy	Voter Registry
	Voter Education or Awareness Campaign
	Gerrymandering
	Electoral Dispute Resolution
	Political Finance and Election Expenditure Control

Source : Authors' Conceptualisation

6 Research Findings and Discussion

6.1 Institutional Autonomy of ECP

Independence is an essential characteristic of any institution responsible for conducting elections. While the structure of election commissions varies from country to country, those commissions are considered most successful that offer both a perceived and real tradition of impartiality at all levels of the organization. An exercise in strengthening the independence of an election commission is, unquestionably, a fundamental and essential starting point toward enhancing public confidence while offering greater assurances among both voters and candidates that their fundamental human rights are being protected.

Without a foundation of independence and unless election administrators are regarded as genuinely as fair arbiters, neither voters nor candidates can be entirely certain that the 'rules of the game' have been followed and that candidates selected by the people have won an election after all the ballots have been counted.

Research participants were asked to share their views regarding institutional standing of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP). As per law, Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) follows the Independent Model (IM) in its organizational structure. It is not the part of any branch of government and performed its constitutional duties on its own. About the constitutional position of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP), respondents showed considerable satisfaction upon institutional autonomy of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP).

“Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) is not a functionary of executive branch of government, nor is it any direction relation with the judiciary”. (A Respondent)

All, the executive machinery, is bound by law to assist Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) in execution of its functions. They couldn't reject any summary forwarded by the commission. The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has constitutional powers to summon any of executive agencies upon negligence. However, respondents were of view that things are not as smooth as they were written in books of law.

One of the major finding of this section of discussion was that the constitution or other electoral laws in Pakistan do not bars higher judiciary (Supreme Court and High Courts) from interference in matters of election commission. Contrary to that, in the constitution of India it was explicitly mentioned that “during an election cycle, no authority including Supreme Court of

India (SCI) can interfere in a matter which is under consideration of Election Commission of India (ECI)”.

Further, Law did not allow any transfers in civil administration without prior permission of Election Commission of India (ECI). The case of appointment of Army Chief on India was well known and is quoted by one of the retired personal of election commission. During the last election cycle in 2013, national government solicited twice the position of Election Commission of India (ECI) on appointment of army chief.

The case of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP), however, is very weak in this regards. Respondents were of the view that judicial activism in election related matters has made Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) a toothless organization. They seemed convinced that Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) had failed to establish its constitutionally mandated position. Majority of respondents believed that poor image of the organization mobilized the public opinion against Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) in the crisis emerged on political screen after the general election in 2013. While discussing the matter with a lawyer, he rightly pointed out that:

“Calling of a sit-in and establishment of inquiry commission to probe allegation made on general election is in itself an acceptance that Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has not performed its legal duties in the desired way”. (A Respondent)

The report of inquiry commission on general election, 2013 re-enforced this perception (The Final Report of the General Elections, 2013). This says, “Taking into account all the evidence on record, notwithstanding the shortcomings of the Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) as mentioned earlier in this report, the 2013 general elections were in large part not organized and conducted fairly and in accordance with the law”.

As pointed out by Alan and his colleagues, most of the respondents are of the view that not all type of autonomies are good for a public office (Catt, Ellis, Maley & Wall, 2015). It is a double edge sword as too many restrictions limited the scope of organization while too much freedom increase the scope of discretion in decision making. Respondents perceive that law has given considerable autonomy to election commission for its operation with a few limitations. Among the limitations, the most important is not restricting the courts from interfering in the election management matters by constitution or electoral laws.

Constitution of Pakistan has been time and again amended to give Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) required freedom and authority to perform its duties. Respondents, however, seemed convinced that Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has been unable to build good will and hence lack credibility. No efforts by the commission has been put into mobilize public opinion in favor of election commission. One retired employee of the commission said:

“Even the inquiry report of the commission acknowledged that despite administrative flaws in election management, it cannot be said with evidence that elections were not a true and fair reflection of the mandate given by the electorate.....This should be the strongest point to build credibility of election commission”. (A Respondent)

6.2 Personal Autonomy

No organization is capable to perform its duties in an efficient and effective manner, unless it possesses the required administratively and technically skilled human resource. Keeping in view this reality and reviewing international literature on election management, this theme was added in the methodology. Respondents were asked about selection procedure, eligibility criteria, term of tenure and removal mechanism.

Document analysis has revealed that Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP), initially, consisted of two members and a Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) to be appointed by the president of Pakistan. President had the discretion to appoint any of serving or retired judge of higher judiciary (Supreme Court or High Court) to be the Chief Election Commissioner (CEC). In 2002, General (retired) Pervez Musharraf, in election order, 2002, increased the number of members from two to four, each from one province (Election order, 2002). In the efforts to make election commission more democratic and to minimize the discretionary powers of president in appointment process, certain clauses were added in the historic 18th amendment in the Constitution of Pakistan, 1973 in 2010 (Faiz, 2015). Appointment procedure of Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) was revised and the authority was shifted from president to the Parliament. Speaker of the National Assembly appoint a parliamentary committee consisting of twelve members. One third of this committee should be drawn from Senate of Pakistan. Half of the members of this committee must come from opposition benches. Prime Minister in consultation with Leader of Opposition forward three names to this parliamentary committee and the committee decide on one name for Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) by applying simple majority rule. In case, if PM and leader of opposition don't agree on single list of three names for

Chief Election Commissioner (CEC), both will send separate lists of three names each to the parliamentary committee.

Compared to South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) countries, the selection process in Pakistan is more democratic and involves Parliament. In India, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka, this appointment is made by the President of respective state. In India, the constitution does not fix the numbers of members of commission. Same is the case with Election Commission of Bangladesh (ECB). Constitution of Sri Lanka is an exception to that. In Sri Lanka though, the appointing authority is president, however, the Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) is appointment from member of commission who distinguishes himself from others in field of administration and education.

Respondents showed their confidence in the clauses of 18th amendment in the Constitution of Pakistan, 1973 related to appointment of Chief Election Commissioner (CEC). However, some participants were of the view that process of appointment is a bit cumbersome. They maintained that agreement between Leader of the house (Prime Minister) and leader of opposition on one name is very rare.

“Appointment of current Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) was delayed for more than a year. Justice (retired) Fakharuddin G Ibrahim had resigned from the post in July 2013 and next Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) was appointed in December, 2014.....The main reason was disturbed political landscape of the country. Opposition was on roads to protest against alleged riggings in general elections.....The apex court had to step in to ask government to make appointment. Interestingly, the appointment was made just a day before final deadline Supreme Court had given to government.” (A Respondent)

Eligibility criteria for a person to be a member of election commission remained an issue in electoral politics. Earlier in the constitution there was an obligation that member of an election commission must a serving or retired judge of Supreme Court. Respondents agreed upon the fact that the job of a member of election commission is purely administrative, not legal. Realizing the need of the day, the 22nd amendment was incorporated into the constitution.

By this amendment, law has permitted technocrats as well as senior civil servant not more than 68 years of age to be appointed as member Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP). Respondents welcomed all clauses of amendment including revision of term of tenure for a member. 22nd amendment has fixed the term of office as five year. It further said that half of members of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) will retire after completion of first two and

half years and other two will retire after completion of other half term. Prior to this amendment, all the four members used to retire at the same time, leaving this constitutional office vacant till new appointments.

Respondents believed that now the post of Chief Election Commissioner (CEC), which is purely an administrative post will execute its functions in a better way. There are no such restrictions in legal provisions of any commission from selected South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) countries. In India, Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) usually came from Indian Administrative Services. In this regard a respondent quoted the example of India thus:

“Amartya Sen, a Development Economist and Nobel Laureate once said ‘If India takes stock of its achievements, the holding of free, fair and credible elections in the face of tremendous odds will be at the top of the list’”. (A Respondent)

6.3 Financial Autonomy of ECP: Resource Crunch

Financial autonomy is an important strategic issue for Election Management Bodies (EMBs) and largely determines their degree of independence from the Government. As a constitutionally independent body, the Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) receives its required operational funding from the annual federal budget through the Ministry of Finance (MoF). Apart from its regular expenses, the Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) also has a supplementary budget for electoral activities and special projects, including conduct of elections, preparation and revision of electoral rolls, Information Technology (IT), infrastructure etc. The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) can re-appropriate its allotted funds as it feels fit. The current financial autonomy that the Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) enjoys is based on an Office Memorandum (OM) of the Finance Division (FD), but no concrete legislation is in place. A respondent from the budget wing told that:

“Ministry of Finance (MoF) had issued a notification undersigned by a section officer which allows Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) to transfer funds from one head to another head of expenses and that all.” (A Respondent)

No other concrete piece of legislation had been enacted by the legislature which could deal with financial matters. He further added:

“The position of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has been compromised on many occasions due to this interference of Ministry of Finance (MoF) in financial matters of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP)”. (A Respondent)

The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has the power to upgrade or re-designate any post and promote its staff. However, it does not have the power to create new or abolish existing posts as its needs change. New posts are created by the Finance Division (FD) and sometimes require the approval of the Prime Minister. The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) establish a committee under the chairmanship of the Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) comprised of representatives of the Finance, Establishment and other divisions to recommend the creation of new Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) posts. Their recommendations are then approved by the government.

“Election commission has raised a very important issue with government a number of times but did not get any reasonable response. Commission was of the view that it should be entitled to a portion from its incomes like nominations papers fee, SMS charges to find polling stations and votes etc. However, government had not decided on the matter. Resultantly, all the money Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) receives in any form had to be deposited in federal consolidated fund.” (A Respondent)

“Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) in collaboration with (NADRA) started checking of voter registration by sending CNIC number to 8300. This service earned money in millions as the rate of one SMS sent to 8300 was charged at RS. 2 + tax. Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) did not get its share from this income as Ministry of Finance (MoF) did not take decision on the matter.” (A Respondent)

Previously the budget of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) was not a ‘charged expenditure’. According to law, in Pakistan budget making process, a charged expenditure (also known as Authorized Expenditure) was the one discussed in the Parliament but not presented for voting. However, in a recent move to reform Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP), the office of Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) and election commission were included in budget as ‘Authorized Expenditure’.

6.4 Functional Autonomy

Primary function of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP), under the constitution, is to conduct free, fair and transparent elections in the country. Under legal framework Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) is also responsible for some of the potential non-core functions, for example, political party registration and electoral boundary delimitation etc. The constitution of Pakistan explicitly asks every executive agency to assist Election Commission of Pakistan

(ECP) in performing its duties. It has the power to summon any administrative agency to help performing its functions.

In interviews, general view of respondents was that functional side of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) was more flawed than its legal and electoral framework. The personals of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) admitted the problem but shifted the blame to executing agencies. They also had highlighted the weak electoral framework in this regards. “Operations of the commission”, said a respondent, “are flawed and delayed because these involved a number of other agencies and department which are beyond the scope of election commission”.

Issues in accountability mechanism had compromised the performance of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP). During elections, Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) hired the lower level staff from various departments for election duties. Most of these departments were now under control of provincial government after 18th amendment. The staff from these provincial departments already knew that election duty last for a day or two but their services in the parent organization are permanent. Their promotions, transfers and appraisals were dependent on provincial government especially Members of Provincial Assemblies (MPAs). On the other hand, Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) did not any have any control on them. At maximum, Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) would suspend there election duty and wrote to parent organization to inquire the suspect. The Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) did not have any authority to suspend him from service or to inquire him at its own.

In India, the commission enjoys absolute autonomy in this matter. In a recent interview, the spokesperson of Election Commission of India (ECI) told press that:

“Even on suspicion of phone calls from candidates to staff on election duty; Election Commission of India (ECI) took action against the suspect. Election Commission of India (ECI) had been authorized by law to suspend from service and charge the convict after conducting inquiry. ECI had worked on a number of such cases to set strong precedents to establish its constitutional position.”

However, in Pakistan no legislation allows Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) to make an inquiry and take action against the polling staffs who are suspects.

During the fieldwork, various regional and district offices of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) were visit to conduct interviews. Four out of four district offices were established in rented residential buildings. The working conditions were extremely poor and places were in

poor conditions. They were short of printers, scanners and photocopier machines. Space at offices was very small and rooms were over crowded to accommodate staff. There were 4-5 employees per room. A District Election Commissioner (DEC) told that:

“We not have enough staff even for routine matters, how will we manage a huge exercise like general elections with such number of staff.” (A Respondent)

International foundation for electoral system (IFES), in 2014, published a brief on Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) which states that as of 11 May 2013, total number of people working with Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) were 2,228 out of which only 1.8% were women (Justice et al., 2014). It means that only 42 women were working with election commission of Pakistan which highlighted the wide gender inequality in working environment of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP). There was no single woman in senior management of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP).

In international practice, there were some success stories in which non-core function to be assigned to some other institution. Non-core activities included boundary delimitation, voter registration, the registration and funding of political parties, electoral dispute resolution, the certification and announcement of election results, and voter education and information. A Former secretary of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) briefed in detail about the advantages and disadvantages of non-core functions. He said that:

“Performing these non-core functions by any other organization can help ECP to concentrate on its core functions....ECP does not possess enough funds and staff to manage both core and non-core functions simultaneously.” (A Respondent)

Comparison of selected South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) countries revealed that in India and Sri Lanka functions like delimitation of boundaries are performed by delimitation commission of those states (*Table 3*). In Pakistan all election related activities including non-core functions are performed by Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP).

Table 3: A Comparison of EMBs of Selected SAARC Countries

	Pakistan	India	Bangladesh	Sri Lanka
Composition	Chief election commissioner and four members.	President may fix the number from time to time.	Chief election commissioner and not more than four members.	Five members and a CEC from amongst them.
Appointing authority	Prime Minister in consultation with Leader of Opposition.	President, subject to any law passed by the Parliament.	President, subject to any law passed by the Parliament.	President
Eligibility Criteria	Retired judge, senior civil servant or technocrats.	Not specified (Generally from Indian Administrative Services)	Not specified	Not specified
Term of office	Five years, half of them retire after two and half years.	Not fixed	Five years	Five years
Distinction				PM, Speaker, Leader of Opposition, one person appointed by President and one person nominated by Parliament.
CECs So far	18	21	12	NA
Age limit for CEC.	68	65	NA	NA

Source: Authors' Conceptualization

7 Conclusion

The research concludes that there are multiple models of election management bodies adopted and practiced in different states worldwide. They are broadly categorized into three main categories: The Governmental Model (GM), The Independent Model (IM) and The Mix Model (MM). Different states adopt different models; some models are very successful and others are

not. The key element behind the success of any model of Election Management Body (EMB) is the degree of its autonomy.

Although Pakistan has adopted an Independent Model (IM) of Election Management body (EMB) in theory but in practice excessive judicial activism and outreach and lacunas in electoral legislature are the biggest hurdles in election management autonomy. Financial Autonomy (FA) of Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has been compromised due to lack of clear legislature in this regard. In addition lack of proper infrastructure and human resource make Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) a toothless organization. Such as, Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) does not have powers to hold returning officers accountable.

There exists a strong perception that Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has been unable to mobilize public opinion in its favor. This has led the organization to face bitter criticism on various forums. Efforts to reform ECP are not given due importance as many actors see these efforts as non-serious and politically motivated.

The latest legislation enacted by the Parliament, the Election Act 2017, is an important document in electoral framework. It was a very serious attempt to reform election commission as well as in unification of electoral framework in one concrete piece of legislation. However, both national and international observers still have reservations about this legislation. It does not give enough autonomy to Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) on the accountability issues of returning officers and other polling staff.

In this regard, Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) can do is to suspend them from election duty and ask the parent organization to inquire. Secondly, the matter of judicial activism is also not settled in this piece of legislation. These non-issues have become the biggest hurdles in the way of an autonomous Election Management Body (EMB). To represent the true mandate and to reflect the genuine will of people in political process, Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) has to come up on the screen as the forerunner of the institution of democracy. It is the fountain head from where all kind of powers generates in a political system. No actor in a democracy can undermine its importance.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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